

VOS Viewer Application Literature Analysis and Scientific Landscape Visualization of Party Leaders and Leadership

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Abstract: This article intends to chart the evolution of the concepts of "Party Leaders and Leadership Selection" in 195 articles spanning 84 years (1937–2021) and "Party Leadership" in 160 papers spanning 60 years (1961–2021), sourced from the reputable international journal Scopus Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q4. Identify the Basic Concepts of "Party Leadership" and Variants of Party Leadership using the Harzing Publish or Perish (PoP) tool and retrieve data sources. In addition, the findings of the full article are revealed, including the number of citations, the name of the publisher, the location of the research, the author's country of origin, and the trends in leadership themes. The methodology in this paper's data is processed using the VOS Viewer bibliometric program, which visualizes title mapping and party leader or party leadership themes. Based on the findings of this review, political scientists should conduct additional research on a variety of topics, including the leadership and leadership of political parties in contact with communication, and the leadership of political parties in the face of the growing threat of political party oligarchy. This problem can be understood in terms of major obstacles to lowering the quality of political party leadership, namely the weakening of the selection procedure for leaders and political party leadership, and the problem is still weak in terms of strengthening political party leaders and leadership. Based on the results of the study, it is very important for the study of political parties to improve the quality of the selection of political party leaders through strengthening the selection of party leaders.

Keywords: Party Leader, Party Leadership, Selection, Strengthening, Network, Mapping

I. INTRODUCTION

This article explores the idea map of "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership" in all renowned international journals from the beginning of publishing till 2020. (Scopus). This article also analyzes the most recent advances in the two concepts presented in a paper between January 2021 and May 2022 at the conclusion of the study. Examining publishing results, reviewing linkages and connectedness in the VOSViewer network, finding sub-topics that dominate, and the sustainability of leadership studies are the two primary items to consider while mapping the two ideas. These diverse dynamics of large political parties need a systematic examination of political party leaders and leadership. Norris (2006) says that

the level of democratization inside a party depends on the quality of its leadership.

This research's significance necessitates the continuation of the most recent study from the previous year. We may outline numerous new subjects from more than 50 articles on the publication of Party Politics from various articles on Party Leaders and Party Leadership between the publications of 2021 and 2022 in May. Local Party Leaders (Broockman, 2021), Intraparty Conflict (Jager, 2021), Electoral Performance (Ennsner, 2021), Masculinity and Voter Motivation (Rombi, 2021), Selection Rules (Marino, 2021), and The Rise and Fall of Party Leaders (Vicentini, 2021). Research done in the past two years points to a rise in internal party conflicts, such as disagreements within the party, a stronger effect of gender and masculinity, and oligarchic rivalry among voters in response to party problems.

While the subject of "party leadership" receives less attention, Several voting behavior subtopics (Roe-Crines, 2021); The Role of Issue Specialization (Meyer, 2021); model selection (Heppell, 2021a); nomination preferences (Heppell, 2021b); Party Leadership election (Heppell, 2021c); Party Leadership contests (So, 2021; Page, 2021; Murr, 2021); Party Leadership changes (Cozza, 2021). Through the quality of political party leadership and election models, this sub-topic shift increases voting behavior. Another issue is voters' preferences in party leader elections, which are linked to ideological poverty and long-term crises. Through masculinity and femininity, in believing parliamentary leaders through party allegiance, belief in the party leadership model is challenged with options and gender roles. Based on the numerous articles published in the last two years (2021–2022) about political party leaders and leaders, emerging networks and scientific landscapes on the study of political parties in various countries may lead to various research subtopics.

II. METHODS

The VOSViewer application was used in this study to visualize the bibliometric network of scientific publications in various Scopus international journals by collecting publications

on "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership" through the Harzing Publish or Perish (PoP) application, which included journals, researchers, or individual publications, citations, bibliographies, and associations with authors. The goal of the bibliometric analysis is to find out how many articles have been written about Party Leader and Party Leadership, how they relate to each other, and how they link to other articles. It also wants to find out which subtopics are most important and what effect they will have on political party research in the future.

The first stage in the data processing procedure is to: Make a file Create a map based on text information. Read information from the reference manager's files. In RIS, select the files "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership." Choose only the Title Field for complete counting. Of the 541 terms, 541 fulfill the threshold, and then we find that for each of the 541 terms, a relevance score is generated, and the most relevant one is chosen based on this score. The default option is to choose the top 60 percent most relevant phrases. So there are 541 terms to choose from. The data was processed, and the terms were sorted from the largest to the lowest proportion, as well as their relevancy. The next step is to use "Yes" to show a group of items rather than all of them. Network visualization, overlay visualization, and density visualization are the three types of visualization. We chose Network Visualization in this literature review.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Articles, book chapters, books, and reviews were used to compile a review of the literature on party leaders and party

leadership. 341 publications were found through the normal processing of data in international journals that use Scopus.

Figure 1. Figurative Publications on "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership" in Number and Type

Of course, given the above-mentioned number of publications, a new concern emerges as to the extent to which the findings of scientific publications impact the relationship between the authors and the citation of the paper's work. 142 articles (71.79 percent), 31 book chapters (15.89 percent), 5 books (2.56 percent), 14 reviews (7.17 percent), 1 brief survey (0.51 percent), 2 notes (1 percent), and 2 editorials make up the scholarly contribution to the topic of "Party Leader" (1 percent). Even though there were 119 articles, 26 book chapters, 10 reviews, 4 books, 3 notes, 1 erratum, and 1 letter about "Party Leadership,"

Table 1. lists the Top Ten Authors in the Categories of "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership."

Authors	Publication	Citation	Affiliation	Country
"Party Leader"				
Cross, W.	4	224	Carleton University	Canada
McClosky, H.	1	221	University of California	USA
Bittner, A.	2	131	Memorial University of Newfoundland	Canada
Costantini, E.	2	119	University of California	USA
Stewart, M.C.	1	91	University of Texas	USA
Bos, L.	1	71	University of Amsterdam	Netherlands
Bean, C.	2	63	Queensland University of Technology	Australia
Pilet, J.B.	2	59	Université Libre de Bruxelles	Belgium
Sanbonmatsu, K.	1	54	The State University of New Jersey	USA
Larsson, A.O.	1	50	Kristiania University College Norway	
"Party Leadership"				
Kenig, O.	1	112	Ashkelon Academic College	Israel
O'Brien, D.	1	103	Indiana University East	USA
Alderman, K.	5	99	CUNY Graduate Center	USA
Harmel, R.	1	99	Texas A&M University	USA
LeDuc, L.	1	92	University of Toronto	Canada
Harasymiw, B.	1	52	University of Alberta	Canada
Froman, L.A.	1	50	University of California	USA
Huitt., R.K.	1	46	United States University	USA
Sinclair, B.	3	39	American University	USA
Von Beyme, K.	1	32	University of Heidelberg	German

It may be classed as the top 10 writers with the most citations based on access results collected from Harzing Publish or Perish (PoP) data. The importance of the issues mentioned in his paper is reflected in the significant number of citations for his work. With 216 citations, McClosky's 1960 article on the relationship between party leaders and followers is the most cited. It is followed by Bittner's 2011 article on the debate over whether the role of political party leaders in elections is determined by the party platform or the personalization of leadership, which has 139 citations; Cross's 1912 article on the growth of the electorate and how it affects the election of a political party chairman, which has 100 citations; and Kenig's 1913 article on the growth of the electorate.

This table 1 can also be used to describe the topic's appropriateness for the intended journal publishing. Journals devoted to sociology and politics, as well as politics and international relations, are the most common places where party leaders are published. The existence of the topic of Party Leaders, for example, corresponds better with publications, according to the table above. The Party Politics Journal has the most articles on the topic "Party Leader," with 11 papers, followed by Parliamentary Affairs (9 papers), Electoral Studies (6 papers), Economist (United Kingdom) (5 papers), European Journal of Political Research (5 papers), British Journal of Political Science (5 papers), The Journal of Politics (4 papers), Journal Elections, Public Opinion and Parties (4 papers), Canadian Journal of Political Science (4 papers), British Journal of Political Science (4 papers), British Journal of Political There are 195 articles in all.

Table 2: "Party Leader" in All Publications

Journal	All Publications
Party Politics	11
Parliamentary Affairs	9
Electoral Studies	6
Economist (United Kingdom)	5
European Journal of Political Research	5
British Journal of Political Science	5
The Journal of Politics	4
Journal Elections, Public Opinion and Parties	4
Canadian Journal of Political Science	4
British Journal of Politics and International Relations	3
Comparative Political Studies	3
Congress and Presidency	3
British Journal of Politics and	3
International Journal of Press/Politics	2
Contemporary Record	2
American Journal of Political Science	2
and Others	124
Total	195

Similarly, the topic of "Party Leadership" is linked to a publication that publishes papers that are relevant to the study's scope. This can be explained by the fact that this issue is regularly discussed and published in the British Politics magazine. 12 papers; 13 papers; Parliamentary Affairs; 7 papers; Party Primaries in Comparative Perspective; 6 papers; American Political Review; 5 papers; Representation; 5 papers; Government and Opposition; 4 papers; Chinese Law & Government; 4 papers; Electoral Studies; Canadian Journal of Political Science 3 articles were published in the European Journal of Political Research. 3 papers published in the International Journal of Press/Politics 3 papers published in Irish Political Studies. 3 Legislative Research Papers. Two papers each were put out by the American Political Research, Asian Survey, and Chinese Economic Studies. Three papers: Congress on Display, Congress at Work, Party Politics, American Political Research, two papers; Chinese Education, two papers; Contemporary British History, two papers; Political Science, two papers; Quarterly Papers, Political Analysis, Political Studies, Quarterly 2 papers, "Politics and Governance". 2 papers: Politics and Governance. Politics and Governance are two papers. The rest, 2 papers There are a total of 160 papers in this collection.

Table 3: "Party Leadership" in All Publications

Journal	All Publications
British Politics	13
Parliamentary Affairs	12
Congress and The Presidency	7
Party Primaries in Comparative Perspective	6
American Political Science Review	5
Representation	5
Government and Opposition	4
Chinese Law & Government	4
Canadian Journal of Political Science	3
Electoral Studies	3
European Journal of Political Research	3
International Journal of Press/Politics	3
Irish Political Studies	3
Legislative Studies Quarterly	3
Congress on Display, Congress at Work	3
Party Politics	3
American Political Research	2
Asian Survey	2
Chinese Economic Studies	2
Chinese Education	2
Contemporary British History	2
Political Quarterly	2
Political Research Quarterly	2
Political Studies	2

Politics and Governance	2
Soviet Law and Government	2
The Others	56
Total	

The Relationship between "Party Leaders" and the Publishers of Different Journals

This argument demonstrates that the topic of "Party Leader" and journal publishers have a symbiotic relationship depending on the right theme or issue. Based on the Scopus search results for "party leader" articles, it was discovered that 195 "party leader" articles were published in the journal "Party Politics". Eleven articles were published online. This is consistent with the mission of this international journal, which is to provide a forum for the study of political parties, including their historical development, structures, program policies, ideologies, election and campaign strategies, and roles in various national and international political systems. "Parliamentary Affairs," a major peer-reviewed publication that covers all aspects of representation and politics related to parliamentary institutions, put out nine sections on the topic "Party Leaders."

Others are as well. Six articles appeared in Electoral Studies, five in The Economist (UK), five in European Journal of Political Research, five in British Journal of Political Science, four in The Journal of Politics, four in Journal of Elections, Public Opinion and Parties, four in Canadian Journal of Political Science, three in British Journal of Political Science, three in The Journal of Politics, three in Comparative Political Studies, three in Congress and Presidency, and three in European Journal of Political Research.

VOS Viewer Visualization of the Party Leader and Party Leadership Network

Its goal at this point is to teach how to use the VOSViewer data analysis tool to develop and visualize the idea of Party Leader and Party Leadership based on article titles using statistical bibliometric analysis to quantify the impact of publications in the scientific community. Network visualization may illustrate the connections between interconnected primary concepts and sub-topics. The term "party leader" has been linked to party loyalty and survival. A party leader's capacity to sustain the continuity of political activity while maintaining the allegiance of followers is tested. Through the party, loyalty is also linked to the voter network, but study findings are still limited. The responsibilities of party leaders shape them and affect how well the party will do in the long run.

Figures 2. A Network Visualization of the Term "Party Leader."

The network visualization graphic depicts the historical link between Party Leader Selection, Party Choice, Party Loyalty, Conflict, Party Leader Survival, Election, Impact, and Role, as well as numerous other issues. The introduction of some of these subjects surely helps to clarify the

emerging theme trend. For example, with 88 words about "Party Leader" and 19 words about "Selection," the correlation "Occurrence" was enhanced between distinct networks of events. More precisely, the "Occurrence" match between big topics about Party Leader (88 words) and correlations of other

topics such as Party Leaders (15 words), Party Member (3 words), Party Choice (3 words), political party leader (3 words), Party Leader Survival (3 words), regional party leader (2 words), party leader selection (2 words), and key party leader (2 words) was discovered based on the results of the VOSViewer bibliometric analysis. The second section examines the relationship between some of the most important emerging election topics. election with 19 words, election outcome with 3 words, electoral performance with 3 words, Labor, vote, trading 2 words, followers 2 words, corruption 2 words, politicians 2 words, election campaign 2 words, parliament 2 words.

Various identifications regarding the strengthening of the association between party leaders and leadership reveal that

by employing a mapping pattern, several article titles that are more prominent on the issue of party leader and leadership selection may be identified. Figure 3 demonstrates that the mapping results utilizing the Networking Visualization pattern include numerous linkages between party leader clusters and party leadership clusters. The study's topic is organized into a network of closely linked themes such as leadership, roles, women, parliament, voters, gender, power, and democracy, and this summary gives some information about them. Figure 3 shows groups of colors, which suggests that the different color spaces change over time.

Articles regarding "Selection of Party Leaders and Leadership Using The VOSViewer Application" are shown in

Figures 3

Explaining the topic of "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership"

Using VOSViewer Visualization Results

In Figure 3, we can see from the Network Visualization study that the two issues, Party Leader and Party Leadership, are truly the key concerns in "Selection." From 1937 to 2021 (84 years), articles featuring "Party Leader" (195 articles) and "Party Leadership" (160 articles) published from 1961 to 2021 (60 years); several articles on "Party Leadership Selection" (19 articles) from 1995 to 2021 (or over a 26-year period); Party Leadership Election (24 articles) from 1980 to 2021 (or over a 26-year period) (within 41 years). It is understandable that the issue of leaders and leadership is actually more of a dispute over the selection of political party

leaders and leadership. The remainder are thoughts on "strengthening party leadership" from 1970 to 1974, as well as party leadership styles (7 articles). So far, one of the major concerns of party specialists has been the strengthening of party leadership.

Denham (2013), for example, proposes a pattern of party leadership selection by promoting a formula that increases the party's internal cohesion and public image, as well as the perceived legitimacy of newly elected leaders picked by a large majority of the electorate (Denham, 2013). As stated by LeDuc (1971) in Party Decision-making on the Leadership Selection Process and Party Leadership Selection in Opposition, the dynamics of party leadership selection have been going on for a long time (Punnett, 1971). Furthermore,

educational work, Tse-tung (1970) stressed "Strengthening party leadership" through educational work. Two years later, Yung-Hung pledged to enhance the party's unified leadership, student enrollment, "two controls" and "five improvements" in health movement and family planning work in four consecutive years (1972, 1973, 1974a, 1974b). The relationship between "Strengthen Party Leadership" and cadre schools is examined by Liu-ho (1977). The other side of "Strengthen the Party's Leadership" over enterprises and executing the mass line is seen by HsüEh-Feng (1980). Based on the results of the most recent study, Wang (2021) shows how to strengthen the financial party's leadership in the age of Fintech development.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The VOSviewer application's scientific mapping landscape is actually quite useful for researchers in identifying dominant tendencies and major problems that have threatened the stability of political parties in the past. This article explores the idea map of "Party Leader" and "Party Leadership" in all renowned international journals from the beginning of publishing till 2021. The terms "party leader" and "party leadership" have been linked to party loyalty and survival. A party leader's capacity to sustain the continuity of political activity while maintaining the allegiance of followers is tested. The average party leader has a significant impact on the dynamics that occur in elections and parliament. Political parties have become more relevant and effective tools for state governance through the election of party leaders. Since the 1970s, the dynamics of published articles on party leadership elections have changed. Whether there is a lot of competition for party leadership positions depends on how many voters there are.

Various current concerns have drained the focus of researchers and political party experts, such as democratization and strengthening leadership inside political parties, gender, and the interaction between party leaders and their members. This threat has lowered the quality of political parties, particularly in terms of party leadership selection and solutions, by strengthening political party leaders and leadership. This is especially true in light of the growing menace of political oligarchs. The study's topics are organized into a network of closely linked themes such as leadership, roles, parliament, voters, gender, power, and democracy. The results show that internal party problems, like party disagreements, are getting worse and that gender and masculinity are becoming more important factors in figuring out how to solve problems within political parties. In the future, further research should be done on some of the most recent topics in political communication and leadership, especially in light of the growing menace of political oligarchs.

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